

Manganese(III) Complexes of Salicylidene Amino Acids

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A number of manganese(III) complexes are known but there is no report yet on a bis(ligand) manganese(III) complex of a tridentate dibasic Schiff base¹⁻⁴.

We report here the synthesis of alkali/alkaline earth metal salts of the hitherto unknown bis(salicylidene-glycinato) manganese(III) (salglyH₂ = salicylidene-glycine) and related complexes by refluxing a mixture of manganese(II) acetate, salicylaldehyde and glycine in aqueous ethanol in presence of a large excess of an alkali/alkaline earth acetate (Method A). A dimeric tetraaquo μ -bis(salicylidene-glycinato) dimanganese(II), [Mn(salgly)(H₂O)₂]₂, is also readily oxidised in aqueous ethanol in presence of added glycine, salicylaldehyde and alkali/alkaline earth acetates (Method B). In the absence of alkali/alkaline earth acetate in Method A only the dimeric manganese(II) complex crystallises while in Method B the insoluble dimeric complex remains unchanged. Potassium salt of bis(5,6-benzosalicylidene α -alaninato) manganese(III) complex could be easily obtained following both Methods A and B using α -alanine and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. However by refluxing manganese(II) acetate, salicylaldehyde and α -alanine, (β -alanine, valine or leucine) in presence of excess Na/K/Ca acetates a clear brown-red solution was obtained as usual but no compound could be crystallised.

Na[Mn(salgly)₂] is a uni-univalent electrolyte in methanol ($\Lambda_M \sim 70$ ohms⁻¹cm² mole⁻¹). The compound liberates one equivalent of iodine from acidified KI. The ν_{C-N} and ν_{COO^-} stretches appear as strong bands around 1590 cm⁻¹ and 1638 cm⁻¹ respectively while the aromatic ν_{C-C} appears^{5,6} at

1545 cm⁻¹. The magnetic moments of this and related complexes (Table 1) are in the range 4.75-4.90 B.M. indicating their high spin $t_{2g}^3 e_g^1$ distribution. The expected electronic transitions, unfortunately, could not be identified due to poor resolution. These compounds are the first ever examples of anionic Schiff base complexes of manganese(III). A dimeric manganese(II) complex is utilised, for the first time, as the starting material for the synthesis of a manganese(III) complex.

Experimental

[Mn(salgly)(H₂O)₂]₂ was obtained by following published procedure⁷.

Synthesis of K[Mn(salgly)₂]·4H₂O :

Method A : A hot solution of glycine (0.3 gm in 5 ml water) was added to a hot solution of salicylaldehyde (0.5 gm in 10 ml ethanol) and the mixture was refluxed for 30 mins. To this potassium acetate (3 gm in 10 ml ethanol) was added and again refluxed for 30 mins. Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.5 gm in 10 ml ethanol) was added to the above solution and the whole solution was further refluxed for 2 hrs. The solution was then filtered and the dark brown filtrate was left in a refrigerator overnight. Beautiful shining chocolate coloured crystals were filtered, washed with ice cold alcohol and dried over silica gel.

Method B : An aqueous solution of glycine (0.3 gm in 5 ml water) was added to salicylaldehyde (0.5 gm in 10 ml ethanol) and refluxed for 30 mins. Potassium acetate (7 gm) and ethanol (10 ml) were then added and refluxed for 30 mins. To the above solution was added yellow coloured [Mn(salgly)(H₂O)₂]₂ (1 gm) and the mixture refluxed for 1 hr. to provide a dark brown solution. The solution was manipulated as in Method A.

The compound is soluble in methanol, ethanol, pyridine, dimethylsulfoxide, etc. For the synthesis

TABLE I. CHARACTERISATION DATA OF MANGANESE (III) COMPLEXES OF SALICYLIDENE AMINO ACIDS

Complex (colour and magnetic moment)	Method of Synthesis	% Mn	% Total metal	% N	% C	% H	% H ₂ O
Na[Mn(salgly) ₂]·9H ₂ O (Chocolate ; $\mu = 4.75$ B. M.)	A	Found : 11.2	16.0	5.8	44.5	4.0	11.2
	B	Found : 11.1	16.0	5.8	44.3	4.1	11.0
		Calc. : 11.3	16.0	5.7	44	4.1	11.1
K[Mn(salgly) ₂]·4H ₂ O (Chocolate ; $\mu = 4.82$ B. M.)	A	Found : 10.6	18.1	5.2	4	4.0	13.0
	B	Found : 10.5	17.9	5.4	41.0	4.0	13.1
		Calc. : 10.5	18.0	5.3	41.4	4.0	13.8
Ca[Mn(salgly) ₂]·CH ₃ COO·3H ₂ O (Chocolate ; $\mu = 4.80$ B. M.)	A	Found : 9.8	17.0	5.1	43.0	4.0	9.6
		Calc. : 9.7	16.9	4.9	42.7	4.0	9.6
K[Mn(5,6-benzosal α -alan)] ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Chocolate ; $\mu = 4.81$ B. M.)	A	Found : —	15.2	4.5	54.4	4.3	5.8
		Calc. : —	15.3	4.5	54.9	4.2	5.8

α -salglyH₂ = salicylidene-glycine, 5,6-benzosal α -alanH₂ = 5,6-benzosalicylidene α -alanine,

of sodium and calcium salts, sodium acetate and calcium acetate were used in place of potassium acetate.

Analyses and Measurements: Manganese(III) content of salicylidene glycine complex was determined iodometrically. Total metal percentage was estimated by igniting the complexes and converting to sulphates. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. C,H analyses were done at CDRI, Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibilities were obtained using the Gouy technique with $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. IR spectra were run as KBr matrices.

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References

1. W. LEVASON and C. A. MCAULIFFE, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1972, 7, 353.
2. M. M. PATIL and R. P. PATIL, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 770.
3. K. DEY and K. C. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 66; *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 695.
4. C. P. PRABHAKARAN and C. C. PATIL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, 31, 3916.
5. R. H. BALUNGI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 981.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, 'Infrared spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds', John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1963, p. 201.
7. R. L. DUTTA and R. K. RAY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1818.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium(VIII) Catalysed Oxidation of Dimethyl Sulphoxide with Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III) in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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THE reaction $\text{DMSO} - \text{Mn}^{3+}$ has been employed as a red-ox initiator for vinyl-polymerisation.¹ We have recently reported a kinetic study of DMSO-oxidation by Cr(VI) and Ce(IV) .² Recently we have communicated the kinetics of oxidation of DMSO by chloramine-T(CAT) in acid medium and OsO_4 catalysed oxidation of DMSO by CAT in alkaline medium.³ This present communication concerns with the oxidation of DMSO by potassium

hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium catalysed by OsO_4 .

Materials and Methods:

E. Merck (G. R. grade) sample of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), sodium carbonate free sodium hydroxide, potassium chloride (BDH) AR grade and dimethyl sulphoxide (BDH) AR grade were employed. Osmium(VIII) solution was prepared from Osmium tetroxide. Aqueous solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was stored in dark amber coloured bottles to avoid photochemical reaction. The ionic strength was kept constant throughout the study by using 0.025 M KCl. The rate constants have been computed by the usual tangential method and are reproducible within 3% error.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to be first order in the substrate and first order in ferricyanide. The first order rate constant increases with increasing concentration of DMSO up to a limiting concentration 0.035 M of DMSO. Beyond this concentration, k_1 remains constant indicating zero order with respect to DMSO (Table 1).

TABLE 1
EFFECT OF VARYING SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION
Ferricyanide = 0.00125 M, NaOH = 0.0025 M, KCl = 0.025 M,
 $\text{OsO}_4 = 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$ M, Substrate = DMSO. Temp. 35°C.

[Substrate] M	k_1 sec ⁻¹
0.00205	0.0001636
0.00402	0.000331
0.00717	0.0005155
0.035	0.001395
0.070	0.001727
0.140	0.001727
0.210	0.001727

In the concentration range where the order with respect to DMSO is zero it was decided to vary the ferricyanide concentration. Though it is expected that the first order rate constant should remain constant with increasing $[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]$ to prove the first order nature with respect to ferricyanide, there is a decrease in the rate constant. This apparent decrease in rate may be attributed to the mass law effect. As the reaction product ferrocyanide is formed, it shifts the equilibrium towards ferricyanide and hence the observed retarding rate. This has been independently checked by performing a run with 0.00125 M of potassium ferrocyanide, where there was no reaction at all, confirming our reasoning that the observed retardation with increasing ferricyanide is only due to the mass law effect (Table 2).